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Runtime Reconfigurable FPGA Accelerator for Tactile Texture Classification Based Shallow CNN

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Introduction & Motivation

E-skin to emulate humane touch

- Why this research matters:
 - E-skin enables to detect pressure, strain, and temperature variations, emulating the human skin
 - Applications: robotics, prosthetics, rehabilitation
 - Challenging to process tactile data in real time on resource-constrained devices

Problem statement

AI at the edge

- Integration of AI algorithms allows real-time processing of data
- Different problems for AI integration at the edge:
 - Stringent constraints in terms of power, area and memory
 - Designing custom Neural Networks (NNs) accelerators is a time-consuming, error-prone process

Our contribution

Automated design-flow

- Objective: automated design flow for neural network (NN) accelerators generation on FPGAs
- Key Features:
 - High-Level Input
 - Automated Flow
 - Minimal Hardware Expertise Required
 - Approximate Computing to save on resources
 - Possibility of generating Reconfigurable Accelerators

Dataset

Data acquisition and dataset definition

- Biomimetic finger with PVDF-based sensors (8 channels) screen-printed on a finger-shaped flexible PET sub-strate
- Sensing glove sampling set at 2 kSamples/s per channel to capture the full frequency bandwidth of the sensors (1 Hz–1 kHz)
- 600 trials × 8 textures × 2 velocities × 3 forces
- Data segmented into windows of 300 samples
- Final dataset: 48,000 samples

Proposed CNN model

Shallow 1D-CNN for Texture recognition

- 1D layers to match the format of the input data
- Filter and kernel size optimized during training
- Shallow and streamlined design ensures low inference latency and low energy
- Grid search performed during training to tune the hyperparameters

The toolchain

Integration of different tools

The toolchain

Model definition

The design flow

ONNX model parsing

The toolchain

HLS synthesis

The toolchain

Hardware accelerator generation

The toolchain

Hardware accelerator generation

QAT and Precision exploration

Exploration on quantized precision

- Base model with $\langle 4,2 \rangle$ precision was **modified** by increasing the Dense layer precision to $\langle 16,8 \rangle$, creating a **mixed-precision variant** (*cnn-mxd*). This variant was **fused** with the $\langle 4,2 \rangle$ model, obtaining a **reconfigurable-at-runtime** model (*cnn-rec*)
- Compared to a fully parallelized design, we were able to save 7096 LUTs, 6 BRAMs, 70 DSPs, and 10016 FFs

Future work

Future of this research

HANNES HAND
PROSTHESIS

KRIA
SoM

FPGA
RECONFIGURABLE CNN

- We envision a **fully embedded, on-edge system** for real-time texture classification
- **Sensors** in a Hannes hand prosthesis transmit signals via the CAN protocol to a Kria SoM
- After **signal conditioning** and **digitization** through the **ADC**, data is processed by an onboard **FPGA** for texture classification, potentially driving **e-skin interaction**

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Thank you for your attention

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